

Multifunctional cooperation with purpose to reduce ergonomic risks. A practical case

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Introduction

We will present a project at Scania with purpose to reduce ergonomic risks.

Target

The target was to improve methods for working with brakes, in a perspective of ergonomics and time efficiency. Expected benefits were to reduce risks for musculoskeletal disorders among service technicians (mechanics) at Scania service workshops.

Background

Work with brakes is one of the most common operations at service workshops for trucks and busses. It is a heavy work, often in uncomfortable postures. Service technicians are frequently affected by disorders in back, muscles and joints.

How the project has been run

Ergonomists from the health department have cooperated with a lot of departments in the Scania organization.

Visualization

Visualization has been an essential part in the whole project, from identification of risks to assessment and solutions, and has probably been important for the success. This kind of visualization can probably be used for other projects.

Solutions

To improve ergonomics when working with brakes the solutions includes both new equipment, tools, working technique and new design solutions.

Results and feedback

The results are that working with brakes now can be done with better ergonomics, higher quality and in a more time efficient way.

“The result is striking, not only the shorting in lead-time, but the job can be performed without risking the health of the service technicians” says José Tirado, Scania Iberia.

“Another benefit with this new method is that anyone can change brakes. It is normally a very heavy job that not everyone can carry out.”

This project has been a “door opener” to further cooperation with the department for research and development.